

REVIEW OF THE IMPACT OF MULTIPLE INTELLIGENCE ON THE CAREER CHOICE OF SECONDARY STUDENTS

Mrs. Arya Tawde

Research Guide:

Dr. Judy Grace Andrews

Research Scholar

University of Mumbai.

Abstract

The aim of the paper is to give an overview of the literature that is available to study the impact of Multiple Intelligence on the Career Choice of Secondary Students. The study will understand all the work that has been done previously. It will identify the gaps in the existing literature and emphasize the need for further research. It has been found that schools prepare students to pass examinations but rarely equip them about career opportunities that are available to them according to their innate strength. Multiple Intelligence theory by Dr. Howard Gardner is widely used to know the extent to which students possess different kind of minds and therefore learn, remember, perform, and understand in different ways. The review paper wants to explore how multiple intelligences of the students also help them to choose their career paths.

Keywords: *multiple intelligence, career choice, secondary students.*

Introduction

“Life is a matter of choices, and every choice you make makes you.” (John C. Maxwell).

Every student aspires to be a successful individual when he/she grows up, in monetary terms but many of them are unaware of how to be the one. In the process of growing up their interest varies and they are in a state of flux and thus end up choosing a wrong profession which they find difficult to adjust. Parsons (1909) believed that if people actively engage in choosing their vocations rather than allow chance to operate in the hunt for a job, they are more satisfied with their careers, employers' costs decrease, and

employees' efficiency increases. Exploration, selection, and commitment to a career choice are major concerns for adolescents. **If students broaden their horizon, they can encompass a wider range of multiple of aptitudes, where their natural inclination gets highlighted to choose a career based on their inbound talent. One of the ways to expand on career possibilities is to use the theory of multiple intelligences. Multiple Intelligence theory developed by Howard Gardner (1983) identifies a person's intelligence as well as strengths. The purpose of this review is to study the role of Multiple Intelligence in Career choice of students.**

Howard Gardner propounded a unique contemporary theory of Intelligence known as "The theory of Multiple Intelligences "which appeared in 1983 in his book "Frames of Mind". Howard Gardner of Harvard has identified eight distinct intelligences. "This theory has emerged from recent cognitive research and documents the extent to which students possess different kinds of minds and therefore learn, remember, perform, and understand in different ways," according to Gardner (1991). According to this theory, "we are all able to know the world through language, logical-mathematical analysis, spatial representation, musical thinking, the use of the body to solve problems or to make things, an understanding of other individuals, and an understanding of ourselves. Where individuals differ is in the strength of these intelligences - the so-called profile of intelligences -and in the ways in which such intelligences are invoked and combined to carry out different tasks, solve diverse problems, and progress in various domains.

Research Question:

- 1) Is Career Choice of secondary students related to Multiple Intelligence?
- 2) How is Career Choice of secondary students dependent on their multiple intelligence?
- 3) What is the relationship of Multiple Intelligence and Career Choice of secondary students?

Objective of Review:

- 1) To study the impact of Multiple Intelligence on Career Choices of Secondary School Students.
- 2) To ascertain the relationship between Multiple Intelligence of students and their Career Choice.

Scope of the review:

There are large numbers of studies on Multiple Intelligence of Secondary students in the general population. However, since the focus of this research review is on the

impact of multiple intelligence on career choice of secondary students hence only this particular aspect will be referred in the study.

Method:

The literature search was conducted on the basis of following criteria.

- 1) The search was carried out in the educational context.
- 2) The search was conducted on students.

Review of Related Literature

Studies Based on Multiple Intelligence:

- Wu-Tien-Wu (2004), conducted a 4 year joint research project (1993-2003) in Taiwan. The study reveals the relationship between successful career and successful intelligence. It advises teachers and counselors to use Multiple Intelligence inspired career assessments for the students.
- The Multiple Intelligences Developmental Assessment Scales (C. B. Shearer, 2007), in his article on practical value of application H. Gardner's (1993) theory of multiple intelligences (MI) to the practice of career counselling. He presents an overview of H. Gardner's MI theory and the ways in which educational and vocational planning can be augmented by the amalgamation of MI theory in career counselling in his case study. He represents both objective and subjective views of actual implementation of Multiple Intelligence in real life.
- Saturnino T. Pabalinas (2015) conducted a study on 370 college students in their first year. His study revealed existence of a greater degree of relationship between parents' occupation, age and gender. The first and the second inclinations to multiple intelligences show highly significant relationship on the choice of career.
- MF Lee (2017), the study examined the multiple intelligences, and career interest among engineering students from vocational college at south zone of Malaysia based on Gardner's Multiple Intelligences and Holland Career Interest. A total numbers of 254 students were strata randomly selected as sample. The results showed that majority of the students tend to have Existential, Kinesthetic and Interpersonal intelligence. While for dominant career interest was the Social, Realistic and Investigative.
- S. Rahim-Pordanjani (2019) in a quasi- experimental design study conducted on 30 students revealed that instructions based on Gardner's theory of M.I significantly enhanced the career self- efficacy of deaf students.

- RJ Atela (2019), conducted the study on 490 first year B.Ed students in Kenya. The study found that gender difference exists in specific types but not all types of intelligence and there exists significant high degree of relationship between types of intelligence and career choice.
- AM Azmir (2020) the findings of the study show that there is a moderate and significant relationship between multiple intelligence and career interest of the students. The study also shows that the higher intelligence range, the more congruence are the personality patterns.

Studies conducted in India.

- Studies based on Multiple intelligence in India could be categorized as the one to know the cognitive abilities of the students. The academic strength and weakness of the students related to language learning, Mathematics and Science. Difference in the competence of the students based on the board of education.
- T.S.Anitha (2013) in her study on MI the researcher found that there exist significant difference among the students of government schools and private schools. While comparing gender she found girls level of MI is more than boys. She also found that the government schools students have fetched far better in the 3 areas viz logical, interpersonal and intrapersonal than their counterpart in the private schools. She conducted the research on 240 IXth standard students of which 120 were boys and 120 were girls. The sample was selected randomly and MI Questionnaire developed by Tirri & Nokelainen was used by the researcher.
- While in a study by Rekha. A (2013) a descriptive and correlational study found out the relationship between Multiple Intelligence, Creativity and Achievement Motivation. The outcome of the study reveals a significant difference in the level of Multiple Intelligence with reference to gender than the type of school, locale of school and medium of instruction.
- Seeraj.K (2015) carried a study to know the relationship between Multiple Intelligence and achievement in Mathematics of students at secondary level.
- N Shaikh (2016) conducted a comparative study of Multiple Intelligence on the students in Mumbai division with reference to grades of students studying in VII grades and IX grades. The research found a great deal of difference in Multiple Intelligence level of students of VII & IX grade. The sample size was 4577 of which

2010 were from grade VII and 2567 were from grade IX. ANOVA was used to find the level of difference among students of two grades.

- Anjana Nair (2016) studied the relationship between student related variables and multiple intelligences among higher secondary students.
- Singh Y and Makharia A Sharma (2017) in their study revealed that our school curriculum needs greater infusion of all sorts of teaching to cater to diverse intelligence of our students. The sample size of their study comprised of 1065 school going Indian children.
- S. Khan(2018) conducted a study to know the development of strategies to teach mathematics at elementary level using the multiple intelligence approach.
- **Multiple Intelligence studies carried out in India are not directly related to our topic except two studies which stands out from the rest of the studies.**
- V.Gaundare (2015) conducted a study on 396 MBA students in Jalgaon. The researcher has tried to describe the relation between multiple intelligence levels of students and elements of their career planning. The study was carried out from 2001 to 2011. The study shows the relationship between managerial competencies required for employability and students multiple intelligences.
- SM..Anitha (2018) conducted a study on 894secondary school pupils for measuring Multiple Intelligence and Career Aspirations. The result of the study reveals that there is correlation between Multiple Intelligence and Career Aspirations of Secondary school pupils of Kerala.

Discussion

Going through the literature review from the studies carried out abroad we come across few studies which study the relationship between Multiple Intelligence and Career Choice of the students. Most of the researchers have used the Multiple Intelligence Assessment scale for testing while few of the researchers have constructed the scale. Similarly, many studies are conducted in India on Multiple Intelligence revealed the existence of moderate inter-correlation between different intelligences and academic performance achievement of the students. But we also come across very few studies are conducted to establish the relationship between Multiple Intelligence and career choice of students.

Research Gap

After going through the above-mentioned studies, the researcher came across certain gaps in the studies based on Multiple Intelligences. The study by Kerka Sandra “Incidental Learning” was conducted on Adults while C.B.Shearer conducted a case study illustrating the effective application of Multiple Intelligence theory. Most of the studies are conducted on college students. While in the study conducted by MS Anitha, Multiple Intelligence and Career Aspiration of Secondary students is taken into consideration. There are no clear-cut studies that exhibit how study of Multiple Intelligence help students to make career choice in their early adolescent age. What skills are they learning based on their self-awareness and the talent they possess? How can they transform their weakness into strength? Hence the researcher wants to explore multiple intelligence with respect to career choice of secondary students. Career choice is always a perplexing question that every student needs to address.

Conclusion:

If every student is aware of his/her unique multiple intelligence and strength at the right time than their outlook towards choosing their career path would be much more simplified. It would aid the student in their career exploration process. Multiple intelligence assessment only indicates the presence of dominant intelligence trait in students. Further research is necessary in India to study the impact of Multiple Intelligence on Career Choice of secondary students.

References:

- Anjana, B Nair (2016) : Relationship between student related variables and multiple intelligences among higher secondary school students, <http://hdl.handle.net/10603/218082>
School of Pedagogical Sciences Mahatma Gandhi University.
- A.Rekha.(2013) A study of the multiple intelligences creativity and achievement motivation among the secondary school students of Mysore city <http://hdl.handle.net/10603/72544>
Department of Education, University of Mysore
- C.B.Shearer(2007) Shearer, C. Branton; Luzzo, Darrell Anthony Career Development Quarterly,v58n1 p3-13Sep 2009
- Gaundare, Vikas (2015) A research study on the role of multiple intelligences in the career planning of MBA students under North Maharashtra University, .

<http://hdl.handle.net/10603/48042>, : Department of Management, North Maharashtra University.

- J., Atela & Agak, John & Othuon, Lucas. (2019). Relationship between personality types and and career choice among undergraduate students of Maseno University, Kenya.
- Johnson, Kathrine & White, Jill. (2002). The use of multiple intelligences in criminal justice education. *Journal of Criminal Justice Education*. 13. 369-386. 10.1080/10511250200085531.
- Juhari, Muzarina & Ku Johari, Ku Suhaila & Mahmud, Mohd & Rahman, Mohd. (2020). Descriptive Analysis of Multiple Intelligence and Career Interest. 10.2991/assehr.k.200824.159
- Khan.S (2018) Development of strategies to teach mathematics at elementary level using the multiple intelligence approach , <http://hdl.handle.net/10603/307319>, Department of Teacher Training and Non-Formal Education: Jamia Milia Islamia University.
- Kerka Sandra Title Incidental Learning.Trends and Issues Alert No.8 Institution Eric Clearinghouse on Adult, Career, and Vocational. Education, Columbus, OH. SPONS AGENCY Office of... arrangement of the workplace (Brown and Duguid 2000); development of critical reflection skills (Cseh et al.)
- Lee, Ming Foong & Lai, Chee sern & Wahid, W.. (2017). Relationship between multiple intelligence and career interest among the engineering students in vocational colleges. 76-79. 10.1109/ICEED.2017.8251168.
- N Shaikh, Shah Mohd, P Wakpainjan (2016), A Comparative Study of Multiple Intelligences of Students with Respect to Grades, *International Journal of Indian Psychology*, Volume 3, Issue 4, No. 74, ISSN:2348-5396 (e), ISSN:2349-3429 (p), DIP:18.01.031/20160304, ISBN:978-1-365-46362-4
- Rahimi- Pordanjani, Saeed & GHobari Bonab, Bagher & fazilati, mansoreh & Pirbalouti, Mohammad. (2019). The Effectiveness of Instruction Based on Gardner's Theory of Multiple Intelligences (TMI) on Career Self-Efficacy of Deaf Students. 10.24200/IJPB.2019.115518..
- Singh Y, Makharia A, Sharma A, Agrawal K, Varma G, Yadav T. A study on different forms of intelligence in Indian school-going children. *Industrial Psychiatry Journal*. 2017;26(1):71-76. doi:10.4103/ipj.ipj_61_16.

- Saturnino T.Pabalinas Jr.Aldwin M Teves and Karen Luzy Teves (2015),Career Choice : An Analysis of Multiple Intelligences and Socio Environment Factors : International Conference on Trends in Economics , Humanities and Management (ICTEHM'15) March, 2015 Singapore
- Sreeraj .K.G (2015) Relationship between multiple intelligences and achievement in Mathematics of Students at Secondary Level, <http://hdl.handle.net/10603/184540> School of Pedagogical Sciences Mahatma Gandhi University
- SM Anitha(2018), IMPACT: International Journal of Research in Humanities, Arts and Literature (IMPACT: IJRHAL) ISSN (P): 2347-4564; ISSN (E): 2321-8878 Vol. 6, Issue 7, Jul 2018, 167-170
<http://oaji.net/pdf.html?n=2017/488-1533806161.pdf>
- T.S.Anitha, Dr.J.Vannessa,G.Sreelakshmi(2013) IOSR Journal of Research & Method in Education (IOSR-JRME) ISSN : 2320-7388p-ISSN:2320-737X Volume 3,Issue 4 (Sep-Oct 2013,PP 12-18 www.iosrjournals.org [www.IOSRJournal of Research & Method in Education JRME](http://www.IOSRJournalofResearch&MethodinEducationJRME)).
- Wu, Wu-Tien. (2004). Multiple Intelligences, Educational Reform, and a Successful Career. Teachers College Record - TEACH COLL REC. 106. 181-192. 10.1111/j.1467-9620.2004.00327.